

LINGO-CULTURAL PECULIARITIES OF GERMAN AND UZBEK PROVERBS: CONCEPTS, COMPARISONS AND EXAMPLES

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ABSTRACT

In this study, the problem of researching and comparing German proverbs and idioms with proverbs was presented. We have proved that the use of German proverbs, set expressions and all kinds of clichés in our speech allow us to better understand the German character, learn the laws of the language, and allow us to maintain interest in learning.

The culture of speech testifies to the cultural and spiritual heritage of a person, how respectful he is of his native and foreign languages, in which he is able to maintain communication in society. To be able to speak beautifully, and most importantly, to speak and express yourself competently is a whole skill. After all, the communicative component of modern life plays an important role in the functioning of many processes. How we express ourselves, formulate sentences, tie together thoughts, the perception of us by the interlocutor depends. Our dialogue opponent will immediately be able to say what our cultural experience is, how much we read and analyze.

The traditions of the language are most clearly reflected in its expressive means, in particular, in proverbs, they diversify our speech, make it expressive, emotional, lively, figurative, give it national features.

Proverbs and sayings of different peoples of the world have much in common, but on the other hand, they also have their own specific features that characterize the original culture and centuries-old history of a certain people. Proverbs and sayings contain folk wisdom, rooted in the distant past.

Immensely oral folk art. It has been created for centuries, there are many varieties of it. Translated from English, "folklore" is "folk meaning, wisdom." In the scientific use of different countries, there are other terms: German - Volkskunde, in the narrower sense of the word - Volksdichtung; French - Traditions populaires. That is, oral folk art is everything that is created by the spiritual culture of the population over the centuries of its historical life. The roots of German folklore go back to ancient times. Proverbs are reflections of folk wisdom. They are different in origin, making our speech more

vivid and expressive. V. I. Dal characterizes proverbs as follows: "Proverbs are a genre of folklore, an aphoristically concise, figurative, grammatically and logically complete saying with an instructive meaning in a rhythmically organized form."

Sayings and proverbs are German folklore. They are part of the national culture; speech genre of folklore and are used in speech, by the way, by the way. They are meaningful, brief, figurative, therefore they are more vivid and accessible material, oriented by its content to a person; character traits, actions, relationships in society and family. They also reflect the life and customs of native speakers, teach a lot, educate, help to understand the moral values of the people who created them. With the help of proverbs and sayings, you can accurately and clearly express your thoughts.

The emergence and development of proverbs and sayings dates back to ancient times. Since ancient times, people cared not only about food, housing and loved ones. He sought to understand the world around him, compared various phenomena, created something new in nature and in his imagination. Centuries-old observations of the people, their dreams and hopes were embodied in proverbs and sayings.

Proverbs and sayings belong to the folklore genre. A proverb is a popular saying, which expresses the opinion not of individuals, but of the people's assessment, the people's mind. It reflects the spiritual image of the people, aspirations and ideals, judgments about various aspects of life.

Created over the centuries, passing from generation to generation, proverbs and sayings supported the way of life of the

people, strengthened the spiritual and moral image of the people.

Let's analyze the existing proverbs in Uzbek and German. In these languages, proverbs are an expression of folk wisdom, it is a set of rules for life, practical philosophy, historical memory. What areas of life and situations they don't talk about, what they don't teach!

Proverbs reflecting the socio-historical experience of the people

Wer zuletzt lacht, lacht am besten

Wes das Herz voll ist, des geht der Mund über.

Vorsicht ist besser als Nachsicht.

Vier Augen sehen mehr als zwei

Besser schießen als blind sein.

Bekümmert Herz treibt selten Scherz

Selbst ist der Mann.

Abgeredet vor der Zeit gibt nachher keinen Streit.

Es wird nichts so heiß gegessen, wie es gekocht wird.

Proverbs expressing daily life experience of people

Abbitte ist die beste Busse.

Niemand kann über seinen Schatten springen.

Schmäh den Spiegel nicht, wenn schief dein Angesicht.

Ein Löffel voll' Tat ist besser als ein Scheffel voll Rat.

Der Sperling in der Hand ist besser als die Taube auf dem Dach.

Gute erreicht mehr als Strenge.

Demonstrating folk experience, proverbs are focused almost exclusively on a person - his character traits, actions, relationships in the family, team and society, etc. In this paper, the problem of researching and comparing German proverbs with Uzbek proverbs, their application in foreign language lessons was presented. We have proved that the use of German proverbs, set expressions and all kinds of clichés in our speech allow us to better understand the German character, learn the laws of the language, and allow us to maintain interest in learning.

Based on the analysis of data from phraseological dictionaries of the German and Uzbek languages, stylistic and explanatory dictionaries, collections of commonly used proverbs and sayings in German and Uzbek, the following conclusions are made:

Proverbs occupy an important place in the lexical and phraseological system of the German and Uzbek languages. They are

widely represented in phraseology and reflect various spheres of life, such as modern society, collective, family.

The relevance and novelty of this work lies in the following: German learners correctly use proverbs in speech, depending on communicative situations, when reading or in direct contact with a native speaker. For a person studying a foreign language and owning a certain vocabulary, phraseological units present significant difficulties, especially if the native language of the speaker does not have a phraseological unit similar in meaning. But if a match is found, then this gives one more incentive to learn German. Summing up, it should be emphasized that proverbs play a significant role in the act of communication and our hypothesis put forward at the beginning of the research work is confirmed: there are significant differences in the figurative meaning of proverbs in German and Uzbek. Therefore, their literal translation from one language to another is not possible.

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